

Consecutive First Order Reactions : Part—II. Hydrolysis of Dicarboxylic Esters

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Kinetics of acid catalysed hydrolysis of malonic, succinic, glutaric, adipic, pimelic, suberic, azelic, and sebacic esters in dioxan-water and DMSO-water is reported. Swain's treatment has been utilized to separate the rate constants of the first and second steps of the reaction. Increase of the chain length increases the kinetic rate quite in consonance with A_{Ac_2} mechanism. Solvent influences are discussed and molecular radii on the basis of Laidler-Landskroemer and Amis treatments have been evaluated.

A study of acid catalysed hydrolysis of isopropyl acetate in relation to Zucker-Hammett and Bunnett treatments is reported. It is established that isopropyl acetate undergoes hydrolysis by A_{Ac_2} mechanism on this additional evidence of dependence on acidity.

In the previous communication¹ we reported the kinetics of hydrolysis of malonic, succinic and adipic esters in aqueous ethanol and aqueous —DMSO. It was found worthwhile to extend the work to all the aliphatic dicarboxylic esters till diethyl sebacate with a view to elucidate the role of solvent and the effect of increase in chain length on kinetics.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the solvents were purified as reported earlier (loc. cit.) while the esters used are all of AR grade. Dimethyl sulfoxide was used after purification by the method of Roberts and 1 : 4 dioxan was purified by the method of Eigenberger. The physical constants of the esters are given below.

Diethyl malonate b.p. 198°, Diethyl succinate b.p. 216°, Dimethyl succinate b.p. 196°, Diethyl glutarate b.p. 118°/15 mm, Diethyl adipate b.p. 246°, Diethyl pimelate b.p. 149°/18 mm, Diethyl suberate b.p. 131/5 mm. Diethyl azelate b.p. 291°. Diethyl sebacate b.p. 307° and Isopropyl acetate b.p. 86.5°.

Preparation of materials and rate measurements : Preparation of the solutions and rate measurements were as described earlier (loc. cit.).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The reactions have been studied at 50° in aqueous-dioxan and in aqueous DMSO at various percentages of mixtures. The first order rate constants of both steps computed by Swain's treatment² are given below.

1. P. S. Radhakrishnamurti and Prakash C. Patro, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 903.
2. C. G. Swain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1696.

TABLE I

Acid Hydrolysis of Dicarboxylic esters in aqueous-dioxan mixtures.

Acid : HBr	Rate constants $k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		Temp. 50°
Esters	50% : 50% v/v dioxan-water		
	k_1	k_2	(k_1/k_2)
Diethyl malonate	79.37	39.26	2.02
Diethyl succinate	115.8	57.57	2.005
Dimethyl succinate	147.4	73.9	1.995
Diethyl glutarate	214.1	106.5	2.01
Diethyl pimelate	221.3	110.9	1.995
Diethyl suberate	242.9	119.8	2.03
Diethyl azelate	291.1	143.4	2.03

TABLE II

Acid Hydrolysis of Dicarboxylic esters in aqueous-dioxan mixtures.

Acid : HBr	Rate constants $k \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$		Temp. 50°
Esters	60% : 40% v/v dioxan-water		
	k_1	k_2	(k_1/k_2)
Diethyl malonate	45.90	23.11	1.986
Diethyl succinate	87.16	42.45	2.053
Dimethyl succinate	100.6	49.93	2.015
Diethyl glutarate	164.5	82.22	2.001
Diethyl pimelate	199.8	97.88	2.041
Diethyl suberate	209.6	103.80	2.020

TABLE III

Acid Hydrolysis of Dicarboxylic Esters in aqueous-dioxan mixtures.

Acid : HBr	Rate constants $k \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$		Temp. 50°
Esters	70% : 30% v/v dioxan-water		
	k_1	k_2	(k_1/k_2)
Diethyl malonate	43.04	21.22	2.029
Diethyl succinate	74.38	37.02	2.009
Diethyl glutarate	112.8	56.22	2.008
Diethyl pimelate	116.4	60.77	1.920
Diethyl suberate	142.2	70.16	2.027
Diethyl azelate	144.0	72.23	1.985

TABLE IV

Acid Hydrolysis of the dicarboxylic esters in aqueous-dimethyl sulfoxide mixtures.

Acid : HBr	Rate constant $k \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$		Temp. 50°
Esters	50% : 50% v/v DMSO-water		
	k_1	k_2	(k_1/k_2)
Diethyl malonate	108.5	52.78	2.050
Diethyl succinate	152.7	74.89	2.010
Dimethyl succinate	163.9	79.03	2.074
Diethyl glutarate	342.0	171.1	1.998
Diethyl adipate	370.8	184.1	2.014
Diethyl pimelate	423.0	210.4	2.010
Diethyl azelate	538.8	265.5	2.030

TABLE V

Acid Hydrolysis of the dicarboxylic esters in aqueous-dimethyl sulfoxide mixtures.

Acid : HBr	Rate constants $k \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$		Temp. 50°
Esters	60% : 40% v/v DMSO-water		
	k_1	k_2	(k_1/k_2)
Diethyl malonate	95.52	47.77	1.999
Diethyl succinate	119.7	58.95	2.030
Dimethyl succinate	141.0	69.74	2.007
Diethyl glutarate	259.5	129.4	2.005
Diethyl adipate	280.3	140.4	1.998
Diethyl pimelate	349.0	173.8	2.008
Diethyl azelate	384.5	190.8	2.014

TABLE VI

Acid Hydrolysis of the dicarboxylic esters in aqueous-dimethyl sulfoxide mixtures.

Acid : HBr	Rate constants $k \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$		Temp. 50°
Esters	70% : 30% v/v DMSO-Water		
	k_1	k_2	(k_1/k_2)
Diethyl malonate	63.5	31.6	2.008
Diethyl succinate	94.82	47.48	1.997
Dimethyl succinate	115.6	57.28	2.018
Diethyl glutarate	203.5	101.5	2.004
Diethyl adipate	233.6	116.2	2.01
Diethyl pimelate	258.0	128.9	2.02
Diethyl azelate	277.3	138.5	2.006
Diethyl sebacate	307.0	146.7	2.09

Structural factors : It will be noticed from the tables there is an increase in kinetic rate as one proceeds from malonate to sebacate, which indicates that larger the distance between the carbethoxy group the more facile the reaction is. There is correlation between the reaction rate and r , the distance of separation between carbethoxy groups³.

TABLE VII
DMSO-Water mixtures.

Esters	Ist rate constants $10^5 \times k_1 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$r \times 10^8 \text{ cm}$
Diethyl malonate	63.5	1.8
Diethyl succinate	94.82	4.4
Diethyl glutarate	203.5	6.0
Diethyl adipate	233.6	12.0
Diethyl pimelate	258.0	13.2
Diethyl azelate	277.3	17.5
Diethyl sebacate	307.0	20.0

The trend observed is quite opposite to that found in alkaline hydrolysis of these diesters, as well as to what is found in diester cleavages by HBr in acetic acid. The mechanism in ester cleavages by HBr in non-aqueous systems is A_{AL_2} ⁴ whereas in the case of acid catalysed hydrolysis of esters is A_{AC_2} .

Solvent influences : A glance at the table clearly establishes that the reactions are uniformly faster in aqueous DMSO as compared to aqueous dioxan. The reason is quite clear as these acid catalysed hydrolytic reactions are favoured much more in mixtures with high dielectric constants. The same trend is noticed when one compares the variation at various percentages of the same binary mixtures. Increase in water accelerates the process.

*Application of Laidler and Landskroener treatment*⁵ :

The equation

$$S = \frac{\epsilon^2}{2.303 (2 KT)} \left(\frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b_B} - \frac{3 G_x}{2b_x^3} \right)$$

$$= \frac{\epsilon^2}{9.212 KT b_A} \left(\frac{2b_x^3 - 2b_A b_x^2 - 3b_A G_x}{b_x^3} \right)$$

becomes on substitution using the values for acid hydrolysis of esters

$$G_x = 9.1 \times 10^{-14} \text{ Sq. Cm.}, \quad b_A = 1.7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Cm.}$$

$$S = \frac{1.07 \times 10^4}{b_x^3 T} (2b_x^3 - 3.4b_x - 47.31)$$

3. C. K. Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1375.

4. T. P. Visvanathan, Ph. D. Thesis, Berhampur University, 1969.

5. K. J. Laidler, and P. A. Landskroener, *Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1956, 52, 200.

A plot of $\log_{10} k$ Vs $1/D$ are all linear. Using the slopes b_x values have been computed and they are quite reasonable for acid hydrolysis of esters.

TABLE VIII

Esters	DMSO-water mixtures Dioxan-water mixtures	
	$b_x \pm (A^\circ)$	$b_c \pm (A^\circ)$
Diethyl malonate	3.10	3.38
Dimethyl succinate	3.09	—
Diethyl succinate	3.10	3.28
Diethyl glutarate	3.10	3.38
Diethyl adipate	3.10	—
Diethyl pimelate	3.1	3.41
Diethyl suberate	—	3.32
Diethyl azelate	3.11	—

*Application of Amis treatment*⁶: According to the Amis theory for ion dipolar reactions

$$\ln k'_{D=D} = \ln k'_{D=\infty} + \frac{Z\epsilon\mu}{K_1 T r^2 D}$$

r values computed from the above equation are quite reasonable.

TABLE IX

Esters	DMSO-water mixtures Dioxan-water mixtures	
	$r \times 10^8$ cm	$r \times 10^8$ cm
Diethyl succinate	6.23	2.99
Diethyl adipate	6.23	—
Diethyl azelate	5.04	—

r values have been computed for the substrates where dipole moments have been found in literature.

Acid hydrolysis of monocarboxylic esters: Kinetics of acid hydrolysis of isopropyl acetate in aqueous medium has been studied with various catalysts like HCl, HBr, and HClO_4 acid at various acidities. The aim was to confirm by acidity dependence the earlier findings by us that these branched esters also undergo reaction by A_{AC_2} mechanism. The effective order of catalysts is $\text{HBr} > \text{HCl} > \text{HClO}_4$. This is quite in order as established by the work of Bunton⁷ for A_{AC_2} processes. The rate constants are given below.

- E. S. Amis, "Solvent effects on reaction rates and mechanism", Academic Press, New York, London, p. 66, 1966.
- C. A. Bunton, J. H. Crabtree, and L. Robinson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1258.

TABLE X

Ester : Isopropyl acetate.

Solvent · water Molarity of the acids	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	HBr	HCl	HClO ₄
.50 M	16.51	15.12	10.05
.75 M	25.73	23.03	16.35
1.00 M	33.63	28.78	22.08
1.25 M	55.31	38.39	31.99

The Zucker Hammett⁸ slopes are all unit slopes indicating unidependence on H_0 . The slopes with stoichiometric concentration are also linear. The dependence on H_0 does not rule out the participation of a molecule of water in the transition state as there have been reactions reported depending on H_0 yet having a molecule of water like in oxidation of hydrocarbon by V^V and oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI} .

*Application of Bunnett treatment*⁹: According to Bunnett the plots of $(\log k + H_0)$ against a_{H_2O} yield slopes " ω " ranging from -2 to $+7$ for various categories of reactions. The parameters in the present investigation for the three acids are tabulated below.

TABLE XI

Acid	$(3 + \log k + H_0) \text{ Vs } a_{H_2O}$
	ω
HBr	+5
HCl	+4
HClO ₄	+3.34

All the values are above $+3$ indicating similarity to acid catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl acetate¹⁰. ($\omega = 4.15$) where undoubtedly the reaction mechanism is A_{AC_2} . The ω parameters seem to establish the mechanism for branched esters is A_{AC_2} as postulated by us in our earlier communication.

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- J. F. Bunnett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4956, 4968, 4973, 4978.
- J. E. Leffler, and E. Grunwald, "Rates and Equilibria of Organic reactions", John Wiley and Sons, New York, London, p. 287, 1963.